

CHANGES IN THE HEMOSTASIS SYSTEM DURING THE PROCEDURE IN ADULT PATIENTS UNDERGOING HIP AND KNEE ENDOPROSTHESIS

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In adult patients undergoing hip and knee endoprosthetic surgery, EChT prolongation, plasma concentration of factor VIII and Willebrand factor decreased in different subjects during the procedure. At the same time, prothrombin time was prolonged, prothrombin 1+2 and thrombin - cases such as a decrease in the concentration of fragments of the antithrombin complex in the blood plasma were observed. In addition, a statistical decrease in the amount of platelets and fibrinogens in the blood was observed. its concentration in the blood taken from the treated area was higher than in the general circulating blood. In the investigation conducted by Dahl O.E. in 2013, high levels of prothrombin1+2, TPA, PAI-1 and interleukin-6 were detected. In a special experimental investigation conducted by this author in 2013, blood taken from the femoral vein on the operated side of patients undergoing surgery revealed local activation of hemocoagulation in the operated area. It was found that the thrombin-antithrombin complex increased 25 times, and the tissue activator of plasminogen increased 7 times in the circulating blood in the area where the operation was performed. Therefore, the amount of TPA in the arterial blood was significantly decreased compared to the amount in the venous blood. This indicator indicates that TPA binds to blood fibrin in the pulmonary capillaries and is filtered from the circulating blood there.

Similar results were observed in the experiment conducted by Eriksson B.I in 2011. During the examination, blood is taken from the patient's healthy side and the side being operated on, and the operation is performed simultaneously. TPA and PAI-1 factors were found to be higher in the blood taken from the treated area compared to the blood taken from the healthy side. When studying the effect of the thrombocyte part of the hemostasis system on hip and knee joint endoprosthetics, it was found that platelets were significantly activated during the procedure. As evidence of this, it was shown that the concentration of β -thromboglobulin in the α -granules released from activated platelets increased

by 200% [28]. All of the above shows that during surgery and blood loss, the body's hemostasis system is activated, and in addition, blood clotting factors this system is also activated when received. At the same time, the blood's antithrombotic reserves, i.e., antithrombin III, protein C, tissue factor inhibitory pathway (TFPI), heparin II cofactor, decrease, and this, in turn, leads to the complications of dangerous thrombus formation. leads to. Against the processes of hypercoagulation and microthrombi formation, the amount of TPA involved in fibrinolysis in the damaged vessel increases, D-dimer is formed in the plasma, and the inhibitor of plasminogen activator type 1 (PAI-1) also increases. At the end of the operation, dissolved fibrin and a slightly increased concentration of fibrinogen were detected in the blood plasma [24]. The above data lead to a significant activation of the hemostasis system associated with the surgical procedure and a significant increase in natural anticoagulants and factors included in their composition. causes slowing down of blood coagulation within the framework of physiological hemostasis in the vein. All this leads to the fact that hip and knee joint endoprosthesis is highly traumatic and leads to a high level of imbalance of the hemostasis system. After hip and knee joint endoprosthetics, hypercoagulability was observed in the blood of patients, and blood coagulation factor VIII, Willebrand factor, and fibrinogen increased.) increases progressively and markers such as platelet factor IV and β -thromboglobulin also increase. Platelet aggregates are detected in the circulating blood. 3 days after the operation, the concentration of fibrin monomers, α 2-antiplasmin and tissue plasminogen increase. a decrease in the level of activator was observed. Observations by Cassis J in 2012 show that the level of plasminogen activator inhibitor (PAI-1) antigen increases 3 times (225%) in the postoperative period. All this is due to an increase in the time of euglobin lysis. The concentration of PAI-1 in patients with deep vein thrombosis was higher than in patients without this complication. In the same study, in the observations made with cells, the authors found that PAI-1 was not yet detected in the patient's blood plasma, but stimulated the release of PAI-1 from the vascular endothelium [38]. possible thromboembolic complications in the patient were correctly correlated. PAI-1 decreased, plasmin-antiplasmin complex and TPA increased on the 3rd and 7th days after the operation[40]. On the 4th day after the operation, all It was found that the amount of VIII:C, Willebrand factor and fibrinogen increased in patients. In addition, it was found that the amount of α 2-antiplasmin increased [39]. At the same time, on the 3rd and 5th days after the operation, the amount of antithrombin III, protein C,

heparin II cofactor normalization was observed. However, the amount of TFPI was at a low level until the 7th day after the operation. The authors noted that the amount of TFPI in hip and knee endoprosthetics is 2 times lower than in cholecystectomy [30]. Linblad. Observations made by B [41] show that antithrombin III, thrombin time and α 2-macroglobulin decreased on the 4th day after the operation. In retrospective analyzes conducted by Amesen I in 2003, it was found that the amount of fragment prothrombin 1+2, thrombin-antithrombin complex in patients with thromboembolic complications was 2-5 times higher than in patients without complications [42]. shows that it decreases on the first day after the operation, and reaches the normal level by the last week after the operation [33]. an increase in plasma concentration was observed in many patients. However, when comparing patient groups with or without postoperative venous thrombosis, no correlation was found between platelet count and activation and the fact of venous thrombosis [35].

Therefore, taking into account risk factors such as the patient's age, hypercoagulability factors in the hemostasis system before the operation, hip and knee joint endoprosthetics in elderly patients may cause complications such as venous thrombosis and pulmonary embolism. increases the risk. This situation is confirmed based on clinical and epidemiological data. If preventive measures are not taken before hip and knee endoprosthetics, in the experiment conducted by Planes A, the formation of deep vein thrombosis 50 %, Brothers T.E, Frank C.E [43] observed complications of deep vein thrombosis in 80% of patients. After other types of surgery, these complications were observed in 20% of patients. These data have been used to confirm venous thrombosis for many years. It was determined by high-sensitivity, objective method-contrast X-ray phlebography, which is the gold standard in detection. In contrast to evaluation based on clinical signs, it allows to determine the true values of the frequency of venous thrombosis. Fatal complications of pulmonary embolism after hip and knee arthroplasty Johnson R Coventry research It is 18-35%. Venous thromboembolic complications (VTE), which include deep vein thrombosis (DVT), saphenous vein thrombophlebitis and pulmonary embolism (PE), have remained for many decades the most important clinical problem affecting the professional sphere of doctors of all specialties without exception. The importance of OBEs is due to their extremely high potential risk to the health and life of the patient [65]. Every year, 50-70 new cases of thrombotic lesions of the venous bed of the lower extremities, primarily deep veins, are recorded per 100,000 population. In elderly and senile age, the frequency of DVT

increases several times (up to 200 cases per 100,000 population per year). Pulmonary embolism is registered annually with a frequency of 35-40 per 100,000 people. According to other data, every year in the general population, DVT and PE are diagnosed in 50-160 people per 100,000 population, with a fatal pulmonary embolism rate of 60 per 100,000 population. In Europe, about 700,000 cases of venous thromboembolism are registered annually; in the USA, the incidence is about 100 people per 100,000 population [109, 141]. In a study by Oger E. (2000) conducted in France, the incidence of DVT was 183 cases per 100,000 population [134]. In a study by Heit J.A. et al. (2008), conducted in the state of Minnesota in the USA, recorded an incidence rate of 117 cases per 100,000 population [109], and when carried out in 2005. studies in California White et al. reported 90 cases per 100,000 population [155]. According to experts from the Association of Phlebologists of Russia, the incidence of DVT and PE in 2000 was: deep vein thrombosis - 240,000 cases, PE (including fatal) - 100,000 cases. This situation is typical not only for Western countries, but also for Asian countries, which means that VTE is a global health problem. Moreover, these figures are underestimated, since in the vast majority of cases deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism are asymptomatic. It is known that approximately 60 - 70% of cases of DVT in inpatients remain unrecognized, and PE remains undiagnosed in more than half of the cases and is the first manifestation of DVT of the lower extremities or pelvis.

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